

A STUDY ON AWARENESS OF E-GOVERNANCE AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Cite This Article: K. S. Ramya, "A Study on Awareness of E-Governance and Attitude Towards Sustainable Development", *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology*, Page Number 15-17, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016

Abstract:

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can be used by government agencies to transform relations with citizens. In India, as in much of the developing world, it is not uncommon for rural villagers to travel long distances to government district head quarters in order to submit applications, meet officials, obtain copies of public records or seek information regarding various services. This involves the loss of a day's income as well as the cost of transportation. With ICT, it is possible to locate government services at village panchayath, that provide documents, land records and other public services physically closer to citizens. The study aims at analysing the awareness and acceptance of e-governance provided through village panchayath. E-governance or electronic governance is the application of information and communication technology (ICT) for delivering government services to the beneficiaries. E-governance enhances public service deliver, as well as expands communication channels for citizen engagement and empowerment of the people. E-governance promotes in achieving Sustainable Development. Sustainable Development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Sustainable Development is generally thought to have three components: environment, society, and economy. E-governance promotes in achieving economic, social and environmental development. Overall, "the goal of Sustainable Development is to ensure the promotion of an economically, socially and environmentally sustainable future for the planet and for present and future generations. The Awareness of E-governance and the positive attitude of teachers towards Sustainable Development emphasize a holistic, equitable and far-sighted approach in decision-making at all levels of education. The study aims at analysing the awareness of E-governance and Attitude towards Sustainable Development among the secondary school teachers of south Canara District.

Index Terms: Awareness, E-Governance, Attitude, Sustainable Development, Empowerment, Village Panchayath & Secondary School

1. Introduction:

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can be used by government agencies to transform relations with citizens. In India, as in much of the developing world, it is not uncommon for rural villagers to travel long distances to government district head quarters in order to submit applications, meet officials, obtain copies of public records or seek information regarding various services. This involves the loss of a day's income as well as the cost of transportation. With ICT, it is possible to locate government services at village panchayath, that provide documents, land records and other public services physically closer to citizens. The study aims at analysing the awareness and acceptance of e-governance provided through village panchayath. E-governance or electronic governance is the application of information and communication technology (ICT) for delivering government services to the beneficiaries. E-governance is "the use of ICT and its application by the government for the provision of information and public services to the people" (Global E-Government Readiness Report 2004). More broadly, E-governance can be referred to as the use and application of information technologies in public administration to streamline and integrate work-flows and processes; to effectively manage data and information, enhance public service delivery, as well as expand communication channels for citizen engagement and empowerment of the people.

E-governance promotes in achieving Sustainable Development. Sustainable Development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Sustainable Development is generally thought to have three components: environment, society, and economy. E-governance promotes in achieving economic, social and environmental development. Overall, "the goal of Sustainable Development is to ensure the promotion of an economically, socially and environmentally sustainable future for the planet and for present and future generations. Sustainable Development emphasizes a holistic, equitable and far-sighted approach in decision-making at all levels. The study aims at analysing the Awareness of E-governance and Attitude towards Sustainable Development among the secondary school teachers of south Canara District.

2. Related Studies:

John (2014) conducted a study on E-Governance in achieving Sustainable Development in Bihar. The study proved the adoption of E-governance promotes Sustainable Development. Seoul (2014) E-governance for Sustainable Development and well being of the people studied how the people adjust themselves in terms of sustainable natural resource management amidst current mainstream development aiming at modernization and economic growth, and state policies of natural resource management relating to the globalization system.

Golok Kumar (2015) made an attempt to study E-governance and its impact on Sustainable Development. The study was undertaken in small and medium enterprises in Delhi proved that E governance bring efficiency in information delivery and optimize performance in decision making among stakeholders. Mehdi (2015) attempted to study on effectiveness of E governance in local self government. The study was exploratory in nature. The study found that E governance improve efficiency, effectiveness and transparency of governments. Though many studies have been undertaken to study e governance in relation to Sustainable Development, the investigator found no studies with regard to Awareness of E-governance and Attitude towards Sustainable Development among secondary school teachers. Hence the investigator made an attempt to study the Awareness of E-governance and Attitude towards Sustainable Development among the secondary school teachers of south Canara District.

3. Operational Definition:

Awareness of E-Governance: In the present study the Awareness of e governance means the awareness among secondary school teachers about the use of information and communications technologies by government through village panchayath to enhance the range and quality of information and services provided to citizens.

Attitude Towards Sustainable Development: In the present study the Attitude towards Sustainable Development means positive attitude towards sustainable development.

4. Objectives of the Study:

The present study had been conducted to investigate the following,

- ✓ To study the level of Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers.
- ✓ To study whether there is any significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers.

5. Hypotheses of the Study:

The present study is based on the following Hypotheses, ‘There is no significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers’.

6. Design and Methodology:

In accordance with the objective and stated hypotheses, the design of the present study is of descriptive survey type as it aims to identify the relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers.

Selection of Sample: The sample of the study was 60 secondary school teachers drawn randomly.

Tool: The rating scale on Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance prepared by the investigator was administered to collect data.

7. Result and Discussion:

In this study level of Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E- governance has been analysed on the basis of their scores on the tool Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance under three levels high, moderate and low.

Table 1: Level of Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers

Levels	Attitude towards Sustainable Development		Awareness of E-governance	
	No.	%	No.	%
Low	10	16.66	14	23.33
Moderate	42	70	36	60
High	8	13.33	10	16.67
Total	60	100	60	100

Figure 1: Shows the number and percentage of Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers.

A perusal of table 1 and figure 1 reveals that out of the total percentage of Attitude towards Sustainable Development 16.6 percent is in lower level, 70 percent is in moderate and 13.3 percent is in high level. Likewise out of the total percentage of Awareness of E- governance among secondary school teachers 23.3 percent is in lower level, 60 percent is in moderate and 16.67 percent is in high level. From the study it can be concluded that the level of Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E- governance among secondary school teachers is moderate. As the purpose of the study was to find whether there is any significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers the following hypotheses was formulated.

“There is no significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers” The null hypothesis was tested by using Pearson’s product moment correlation. The details of the results obtained in Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers is given in table 2

Table 2: Correlation between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers

Variables	‘r’	Significance
Sustainable Development	1.297	Significant at 0.01 level
E-governance		

(Theoretical value is 0.330, df 60)

From the table 2 it can be observed that correlation coefficient Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers is 1.297 at the degrees of freedom 60 which is more than theoretical value ‘r’ of 0.330 at 0.01 level. Hence it is clear that the difference between two variables is highly significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis titled “There is no significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers” is rejected. In the light of the above result it can be concluded that there is significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers.

8. Findings:

The following are the important findings of the present investigation,

- ✓ The level of Attitude towards Sustainable Development among secondary school teachers is moderate.
- ✓ The level of Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers is moderate.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Attitude towards Sustainable Development and Awareness of E-governance among secondary school teachers

9. Implications of the Study:

Education is regarded as the potential instrument of national development. The teacher have the responsibility of shaping their present and future students to adapt with the ever changing environment to ensure a social harmony. In the man making process teachers should have adequate knowledge regarding E-governance and Sustainable development. The awareness of E-governance contributes positively both socio-economic and Sustainable development. It also helps to strength and the educational process in attaining its main objectives. The secondary school education plays a vital role as linking the development of the child with society and its political productive and socio-cultural dimension. In this regard the secondary school teachers should have awareness of E-governance and positive Attitude towards Sustainable development which leads sustainable society.

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